

A Fluid Dynamics Model for Peripheral Pumps: Derivation, Calibration and Prediction of Pump Characteristic Curves

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Abstract

This study presents the development and application of a fluid dynamics model for peripheral pumps (PPs). Recent research has demonstrated the advantageous meso- and micromixing behavior of PPs and their suitability for mixing-sensitive reactions. To assess their performance as chemical reactors in industrial applications, a detailed understanding of the fluid dynamics within these pumps is required. Existing fluid dynamic models for PPs are primarily designed for pump optimization and therefore rely on detailed geometric data and knowledge of friction loss mechanisms, which limits their accessibility for chemical engineers. The aim of this study is to provide a simplified modeling approach that allows the estimation of the internal volumetric flow rates of PPs based solely on experimentally measured pump characteristic curves. The model is derived from an integral formulation originally developed for side channel pumps and applied to two PPs of different sizes. After calibration using a single pump characteristic curve, the model successfully predicts the remaining pump characteristics with a maximum deviation of 7.7%. The similarity of the calibrated parameters, with deviations ranging from 4.7% to 12.7%,

indicates that they can be reliably transferred between pumps with comparable specific speed and specific diameter. The proposed modeling approach thus provides reaction engineers with a practical framework to investigate the fluid dynamics of PPs and to evaluate their suitability for application as chemical reactors.

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1 Introduction

Peripheral pumps (PP), also known as regenerative flow pumps, are self-priming pumps and are characterized by their ability to generate high heads at low flow rates [1] and their simple construction. These properties have led to their widespread use in industry, including applications as supply pumps in chemical industry [2]. A drawback of PPs in such applications is their relatively low efficiency of usually less than 50% [3], as much of the input energy is dissipated due to internal circulations within the pump. While this may be disadvantageous for pure fluid transport, it results in high specific energy dissipation in the fluid and leads to efficient mixing of the fluid. Recent studies as the one by Ashrafmansouri et al. [4] suggest that PPs can be effectively used as reactors (also referred to as reaction mixing pumps in the chemical industry) and can be a promising alternative to conventional reactors for mixing-sensitive reactions. Additionally, these pumps are often manufactured with magnetic couplings for applications in chemical engineering [5], making them suitable for handling hazardous chemicals. They can also withstand very high pressures in solid construction, enabling reactions to take place under such conditions. Furthermore, their suitability for both single-phase and multiphase applications makes PPs attractive candidates for use as chemical reactors.

Despite their potential, the research on the use of PPs as chemical reactors is limited. To efficiently utilize PPs as chemical reactors, especially for process design, optimization and scale-up, knowledge about the internal volumetric flow rates is required. The internal flow rates particularly influence the reaction performance as they not only influence the concentration gradients on the reactor scale (macromixing) but also the dilution of fresh feed near the inlet (mesomixing). Additionally, the energy dissipated in the pump directly influences the mixing behavior at the smallest scales of mixing (micromixing) [6]. For mixing-sensitive reactions, both mesomixing and micromixing can significantly influence the product distribution. Therefore, high internal flow rates and high local energy dissipation rates are essential to achieve high selectivity toward the desired target products.

The internal fluid dynamics of PPs can be investigated experimentally e.g. by residence time distributions, pump characteristic curves or optical methods as particle image velocimetry measurements. Another possibility is the use of computational methods such as computational fluid dynamics. All of the above are common choices but are very time consuming and expensive and are not necessarily available in early development stages.

An additional common approach is the use of simpler integral or one-dimensional fluid dynamic models. But there exist only a few theoretical models to describe the fluid dynamics of PPs [7]. A detailed discussion on the fundamentals of PPs can be found in Oelrich [8] and Raheel et al. [2]. Fluid dynamic models for PPs can be categorized into two fundamental groups [9]. The first group, based on turbulence and mixing theory, assumes that the impeller torque is transferred to

the fluid through turbulent shear stresses. The second group focuses on the momentum exchange between the flow in the impeller and the side channel. Iversen [10] developed a model based on the turbulent shear stress between the fluid and the impeller. Comparative studies have shown that calculation approaches based on the exchange of angular momentum achieve better agreement with experimental data [11] compared to shear stress approach. Wilson et al. [12] developed a one-dimensional model based on the exchange of angular momentum. This model is derived by arbitrary control elements in the pump and is much more detailed than the previously mentioned models. However, as Wilson [13] pointed out in a following publication, the applicability of this model is limited due to its complexity. Song et al. [3] modified the model of Wilson et al. [12] to the developing region of the pump, in which the circulation flow forms after the inlet. The main downside of the model from Song et al. [3] is that it is not capable of predicting the off-design flow conditions [7] (operating conditions that deviate from the design point).

While these models deliver great insight into the fluid dynamics of PPs, they are often mathematically complex and require detailed information about the pump geometry as well as the underlying friction loss mechanisms. Such models are intended to accurately describe the influence of geometric parameters on the fluid dynamics of the pump and are therefore mostly attractive for the design of PPs itself. Because of this, these models are less attractive for applications in chemical engineering where engineers, especially in early stages of process development, only require good estimates for the fluid dynamics of the pump as the order of magnitude of the internal volumetric flow rates and the macromixing times, respectively. By this, e.g. the estimated internal flow rates can be used to build compartment models for the PPs to evaluate their usability for chemical reactions. Hence, there is a strong need to develop a simpler fluid dynamic model than the existing 1D models for PPs which allows chemical engineers to gain knowledge about the fluid dynamics of a existing PP which requires minimal geometric information and minimal experimental effort.

The aim of this work is to present a simple fluid dynamic model for PPs, which can give estimates of the dominant fluid dynamics of PPs based on limited geometrical information and with minimal experimental input. To do so, a novel approach was followed in this work. As the working principle of PPs is closely related to the one of side channel pumps (SCP), similar modeling approaches should be applicable for both pumps to describe the internal fluid dynamics. Thus, the new model for PPs developed in this work is based on a modeling approach developed for SCPs. A review on available fluid dynamic models for SCPs can be found in [9]. In this work, a model for PPs is presented based on the modeling approach for SCPs provided by Muschelknautz [14]. They follow a modeling approach similar to the one of Wilson et al. [12] but instead of a one-dimensional formulation they present an integral modeling approach for the whole pump, resulting in a simpler model formulation. It is demonstrated how the modeling approach from Muschelknautz [14] for SCPs can be extended to model PPs. Additionally, some simplifications are introduced as "lumped parameters" which summarize the friction losses in the pump. By this, the model can be easily calibrated using a single pump characteristic curve, which is usually delivered by the manufacturer and thereby eliminating the need for experiments or at least minimizing the experimental effort. The new model allows the calculation of the pressure build-up across the pump for a given combination of impeller speed and nominal flow rate, based on minimal geometric information. First, the new model is calibrated using an experimentally obtained

pump characteristic curve and subsequently applied to predict additional pump characteristic curves. The predicted curves are then compared with experimental measurements to assess the model's performance and confirm its applicability to peripheral pumps.

This work focuses on the development of the fluid dynamic model, its calibration, and the prediction of pump characteristic curves. Methods for extracting internal flow rates and integrating this information into compartment models of PPs will be addressed in subsequent publications. The presented modeling approach is an attractive alternative to full CFD simulations and more complex fluid dynamic models, such as the one from Wilson et al. [12], for describing the internal volumetric flow rates and pump characteristic curves in PPs. Due to its simplicity, it is computationally inexpensive and can be used to assess large parameter spaces. This feature makes the model particularly suitable for the early stages of process development.

2 Derivation of the Fluid Dynamic Model

2.1 Operating Principle of Peripheral Pumps

Figure 1: a) Construction of a SCP (adapted from [12, 14]). b) Construction of a PP (adapted from [9]). The streamlines represent the helical path of the fluid.

PPs are a type of centrifugal pump whose impeller rotates within a housing containing an inlet and an outlet. Their design and operating principle closely resemble those of SCPs.

In a SCP, an impeller with blades on one side rotates within a housing that features a side channel extending along most of the circumference (Figure 1a). A separating block interrupts the channel, dividing inlet and outlet and preventing a direct pressure short-circuit. Both openings are positioned on the impeller side.

A PP has a nearly identical construction but in a mirror-symmetric configuration (Figure 1b). Impeller blades and side channels are present on both sides, and the inlet and outlet are located at the outer radius of the channel. This symmetry results in a strong geometric similarity between PPs and SCPs.

The working principle of both pumps is also nearly identical. The fluid enters the impeller axially, is captured by the impeller blades, and redirected in circumferential direction. Centrifugal forces drive the fluid radially outward into the side channel, from where it is guided back into the impeller. The resulting combination of radial and tangential motion produces a helical trajectory, causing the fluid to pass through the impeller multiple times.

This repeated exchange enables continuous momentum transfer between impeller and side-channel flow and leads to a progressive circumferential pressure increase. At the separating

block, part of the fluid exits the pump while the remainder is redirected and continues circulating.

The main difference between PPs and SCPs lies in the symmetry of this circulation: SCPs operate on one side of the impeller only, whereas PPs operate on both sides. Comprehensive information on the operating mechanisms of side-channel and peripheral pumps can be found in Engeda et al. [1] and Muschelknautz [14].

2.2 Fluid Dynamic Model

Given the structural and physical similarities between peripheral pumps (PPs) and side-channel pumps (SCPs), and assuming a fully mirror-symmetric flow without fluid exchange between the left and right impeller channels, a PP can be represented as two parallel SCPs. This approximation enables the direct application of the fluid dynamic model of Muschelknautz [14] to one half of the PP geometry. It must be noted, however, that this assumption constitutes a significant simplification and does not capture the full complexity of the internal flow. Nevertheless, because the objective of the present work is to provide a practical tool for estimating the fluid dynamics of PPs in the context of their use as chemical reactors, this reduction in detail is considered acceptable. The validity and accuracy of this modeling assumption are therefore subject to evaluation in the subsequent analysis.

In the following, the derivation of the fluid dynamic model for PPs, based on the SCP model of Muschelknautz [14], is presented. This modeling framework comprises three principal steps: (1) determining the circulating flow between the impeller and the side channel induced by centrifugal force differences, (2) calculating the pressure rise in circumferential direction resulting from momentum exchange between the impeller and the side channel due to this circulating flow, and (3) accounting for gap flows between the impeller and the housing. In this work, these steps are revisited with respect to the objective of providing a practical and easily applicable model capable of estimating the fluid dynamics of existing PPs. To enable the direct use and the calibration of the model solely based on one pump characteristic curve, additional simplifying assumptions are introduced. The key deviations from the original formulation of Muschelknautz [14] are explicitly identified, while further details of the original model can be found in the cited reference.

Figure 2 illustrates the geometric parameters of the PPs that are required for the model developed in the following subsections.

2.2.1 Internal Circulation Flow

The fluid in the impeller channel is forced into a circular motion by the movement of the impeller blades tangentially to the direction of impeller rotation, thereby experiencing a centrifugal force. Through convective and viscous transport of angular momentum, the fluid in the side channel is also forced into a circular motion along the circumference and experiences a centrifugal force. Since the fluid in the side channel is driven only indirectly by the impeller, both the velocity of this circular motion and the resulting centrifugal force are lower than in the impeller channel.

Figure 2: Geometric parameters of the PPs required in the fluid dynamic model, a) front view, b) side channel, c) breaker channel. The colored areas indicate the impeller channel (blue), the side channel (green), and the breaker channel (red). The point marks the center of gravity of the side channel cross-section.

Due to this difference in forces, a compensating flow from the impeller channel into the side channel is generated, acting perpendicular to the rotational flow in the channels, i.e., in the axial direction. This superimposed cross-flow causes the characteristic circulation pattern in the pump, as shown in Figure 3.

Muschelknautz [14] represents the combined impeller–side-channel cross section as circular, with circulation entering and exiting laterally. While this is suitable for SCPs, it does not reflect the geometry of PPs. This assumption differs from earlier PP models, such as Wilson et al. [12], which assume that fluid exits the impeller primarily at the blade tip.

Figure 4 illustrates the velocity profile of the circulation flow between the impeller and the side channel. The parameter r_{imp} denotes the mean radius of the impeller blades, as defined in Equation (2.1), where $r_{\text{imp},i}$ and $r_{\text{imp},o}$ correspond to the inner and outer radii of the impeller blades, respectively. The radii r_z , r_1 , and r_2 denote characteristic positions of the circulation flow entering and exiting the side channel, based on the experimental study of swirl flows in pipes by Atagündüz [15]. These positions can be calculated using Equations (2.2)–(2.4).

$$r_{\text{imp}} = \frac{r_{\text{imp},i} + r_{\text{imp},o}}{2} \quad (2.1)$$

$$r_z = r_{\text{imp}} + \frac{d_{\text{sc}}}{6} \quad (2.2)$$

$$r_1 = r_{\text{imp}} - \frac{d_{\text{sc}}}{6} \quad (2.3)$$

$$r_2 = r_{\text{imp}} + \frac{d_{\text{sc}}}{3} \quad (2.4)$$

Additionally, d_{sc} in Figure 4 denotes the diameter of the side channel. Because the PP side channel is not circular as shown in Figure 2, this diameter is estimated using Equation (2.5).

Figure 3: Circulation flow between the impeller channel and side channel. Only a small portion of the channel is shown and depicted as a straight cylinder for clarity; the actual channel is curved. The helical streamline indicates the assumed flow course. The velocity triangles show the velocity components at 1.: transition from the side channel to the impeller channel at r_1 and 2.: transition from the impeller channel to the side channel at r_2 . The colored areas indicate the impeller channel (blue) and the side channel (green).

Here, A_{sc} corresponds to the cross-sectional area of the side channel as shown in Figure 2.

$$d_{sc} = \sqrt{\frac{4}{\pi} A_{sc}} \quad (2.5)$$

The radial pressure rise within both the impeller and the side channel results from centrifugal forces induced by the tangential velocities and can be calculated for one angular position using Equation (2.6), where ρ is the density of the fluid. Since the circulation flow between the impeller and side channel is represented by a representative flow at the radii r_1 and r_2 , the pressure difference between these positions is evaluated.

$$\Delta p_{rad} = \rho \int_{r_1}^{r_2} \frac{u^2}{r} dr \quad (2.6)$$

Under the assumption that the circumferential velocity scales proportionally with the angular velocity as $u = \omega r$, the resulting pressure rise is given by Equation (2.7).

$$\Delta p_{rad} = \rho \int_{r_1}^{r_2} \omega^2 r dr \quad (2.7)$$

For the impeller channel, a linear profile of tangential velocities, as given in Equation (2.8), can be reasonably assumed because the fluid is transported tangentially to the direction of impeller rotation between the impeller blades. The velocity distribution within the side channel, however, is not known. Muschelknautz [14] assumes a linear velocity profile, based on equal tangential velocities at radius r_2 in both the side and impeller channels, and the mean velocity u_{sc} in the

Figure 4: Geometric parameters of the circulation flow according to Atagündüz [15] (adapted from [14]). The black profile indicates the radial progression of the circulation velocity. The gray rectangles represent the average velocities above and below the circulation center. The colored areas indicate the impeller channel (blue) and the side channel (green).

side channel. In this work, it is simplistically assumed that the circumferential velocity in the side channel is proportional to a representative angular velocity, ω_{sc} , as defined in Equation (2.9). This angular velocity is calculated using Equation (2.10), where u_{sc} denotes the mean tangential velocity in the side channel, and r_{sc} corresponds to the radius at the center of area of the side channel cross section.

$$u_{imp,local}(r) = \omega_{imp}r \quad (2.8)$$

$$u_{sc,local}(r) = \omega_{sc}r \quad (2.9)$$

$$\omega_{sc} = \frac{u_{sc}}{r_{sc}} \quad (2.10)$$

By substituting Equations (2.8) and (2.9) in Equation (2.7), the radial pressure buildup can be calculated for the impeller channel according to Equation (2.11), and for the side channel according to Equation (2.12).

$$\Delta p_{imp} = \frac{\rho}{2} \omega_{imp}^2 (r_2^2 - r_1^2) \quad (2.11)$$

$$\Delta p_{sc} = \frac{\rho}{2} \omega_{sc}^2 (r_2^2 - r_1^2) \quad (2.12)$$

To calculate the mean velocity of the resulting circulation flow, Muschelknautz [14] employs a momentum balance between inlet (I) and outlet (II) of the pump, accounting for friction losses through wall friction areas and corresponding coefficients. In contrast, the present work adopts a further simplification by assuming that the circulation flow between the impeller channel and the side channel is driven solely by pressure differences. Applying the Bernoulli equation to the flow between the impeller and the side channel, this process is described by Equation (2.13). Friction losses are incorporated via a single friction loss coefficient, ζ_{circ}^* , which determines the mean circulation velocity u_{circ} as expressed in Equation (2.14). This approach significantly reduces the

required geometric information, thereby simplifying the model formulation.

$$\Delta p_{\text{circ}} = \Delta p_{\text{imp}} - \Delta p_{\text{sc}} \quad (2.13)$$

$$\Delta p_{\text{circ}} = \frac{\rho}{2} \zeta_{\text{circ}}^* u_{\text{circ}}^2 \quad (2.14)$$

By combining Equations (2.13) and (2.14) with Equations (2.11) and (2.12), the mean circulation velocity u_{circ} can be calculated using Equation (2.15).

$$u_{\text{circ}} = \sqrt{\frac{1}{\zeta_{\text{circ}}^*} (r_2^2 - r_1^2) (\omega_{\text{imp}}^2 - \omega_{\text{sc}}^2)} \quad (2.15)$$

Together with the circulation area A_{circ} , the mean circulation mass flow can be determined. Muschelknautz [14] defines this area as the space between $r_{\text{imp,o}}$ and r_z . Since u_{circ} represents the mean circulation velocity, the authors consider it reasonable to base the mass flow calculation on the mean circulation area as half of the contact area between the impeller and the side channel. This is expressed in Equation (2.16), where φ_{bc} denotes the angular extent of the breaker block as shown in Figure 2. The friction loss coefficient ζ_{circ} is reformulated as described in Equation (2.17).

$$A_{\text{circ}} = \frac{\pi}{2} (r_{\text{imp,o}}^2 - r_{\text{imp,i}}^2) \left(1 - \frac{\varphi_{\text{bc}}}{360^\circ}\right) \quad (2.16)$$

$$\zeta_{\text{circ}} = \sqrt{\frac{1}{\zeta_{\text{circ}}^*}} \quad (2.17)$$

Using these definitions and adjustments, the mean circulation mass flow can be expressed by Equation (2.18).

$$\dot{m}_{\text{circ}} = \rho A_{\text{circ}} \zeta_{\text{circ}} \sqrt{(r_2^2 - r_1^2) (\omega_{\text{imp}}^2 - \omega_{\text{sc}}^2)} \quad (2.18)$$

2.2.2 Pressure Build-Up in the Side Channel

The mass exchange between the impeller and the side channel is inherently coupled with momentum transfer, facilitating the transfer of energy from the impeller to the side channel. This interaction drives a pressure buildup along the tangential direction of the side channel. The resulting pressure increase can be derived from the angular momentum balance of the side channel. Since only the tangential component of momentum contributes to the circumferential pressure rise, the analysis focuses exclusively on this component, yielding a scalar formulation. The change in angular momentum across the entire side channel, from inlet to outlet, is expressed as the sum of all acting torques M and the momentum fluxes \dot{L} associated with the inflows and outflows, as given in Equation (2.19).

$$\frac{dL}{dt} = \sum_i M_i + \sum_i \dot{L}_i \quad (2.19)$$

Since an incompressible flow is considered, the fluid transported through the side channel enters and exits with the same mass flow and velocity and at the same radius and consequently does not contribute to a net momentum change. Instead, the angular momentum is transported by the circulation flow as shown in Figure 3.

It is assumed that the flow leaving the impeller and entering the side channel exits the impeller at radius r_2 and can be represented by a simplified flow characterized by the mass flow \dot{m}_{circ} and the tangential velocity $u_{\text{imp,local}}(r_2)$ in the impeller channel at r_2 , as given by Equation (2.20).

$$\dot{L}_{\text{circ},r_2} = \dot{m}_{\text{circ}} r_2^2 \omega_{\text{imp}} \quad (2.20)$$

The flow then leaves the side channel at radius r_1 with tangential velocity $u_{\text{sc,local}}(r_1)$ at r_1 according to Equation (2.21), thereby increasing the angular momentum in the circumferential direction and resulting in a pressure rise along the side channel. Note that the flows $\dot{L}_{\text{circ},r_1}$ and $\dot{L}_{\text{circ},r_2}$ represent the exchange of angular momentum between the side channel and the impeller channel averaged over the entire circulation cross-section A_{circ} , and are therefore included only once in the balance equation.

$$\dot{L}_{\text{circ},r_1} = -\dot{m}_{\text{circ}} r_1^2 \omega_{\text{sc}} \quad (2.21)$$

The pressure gradient along the circumferential direction exerts additional torques (Equations (2.22)–(2.23)) on the fluid at the beginning and end of the side channel (denoted as I and II in Figure 1).

$$M_{p,\text{I}} = p_{\text{I}} A_{\text{sc}} r_{\text{sc}} \quad (2.22)$$

$$M_{p,\text{II}} = -p_{\text{II}} A_{\text{sc}} r_{\text{sc}} \quad (2.23)$$

To account for friction losses in the tangential flow an additional friction loss term M_{fric} based on the mean tangential velocity u_{sc} and a friction loss coefficient ζ_{sc} is introduced, which was not included in the original formulation from Muschelknautz [14].

$$M_{\text{fric}} = -\frac{\rho}{2} \zeta_{\text{sc}} u_{\text{sc}}^2 A_{\text{sc}} r_{\text{sc}} \quad (2.24)$$

Assuming steady-state conditions, substitution of Equations (2.20)–(2.23) into Equation (2.19) yields Equation (2.25), which describes the pressure increase from the inlet to the outlet of the side channel.

$$\Delta p = p_{\text{II}} - p_{\text{I}} = \frac{\dot{m}_{\text{circ}}}{A_{\text{sc}} r_{\text{sc}}} (r_2^2 \omega_{\text{imp}} - r_1^2 \omega_{\text{sc}}) - \frac{\rho}{2} \zeta_{\text{sc}} u_{\text{sc}}^2 \quad (2.25)$$

2.2.3 Consideration of Gap Flows

The pressure difference between the pump outlet and inlet induces gap flows between the impeller and the housing, as small clearances are always present in this region [16]. Muschelknautz [14] accounts for gap flows both, past the pump shaft alongside the impeller and through the breaker gap. In the present work, it is assumed that the primary gap flow occurs through the breaker gap, where the pressure difference is largest. Including both, the breaker-channel flow and the flow past the impeller side, would render the model underdetermined, preventing calibration without additional constraints. The volume between the impeller and the breaker block is referred to as the breaker channel as illustrated in Figure 2b. The gap flow through this channel is modeled as frictional pipe flow according to Equation (2.26), with position I denoting the inlet and II the outlet as shown in Figure 1. In this case, however, the flow is directed from the outlet toward

the inlet.

$$\frac{\rho}{2}u_{\text{II}}^2 + \rho gh_{\text{II}} + p_{\text{II}} = \frac{\rho}{2}u_{\text{I}}^2 + \rho gh_{\text{I}} + p_{\text{I}} + \frac{\rho}{2}u_{\text{I}}^2\zeta_{\text{bc,in}} + \frac{\rho}{2}u_{\text{I}}^2\frac{\lambda\Delta l}{d_{\text{bc}}} \quad (2.26)$$

The contribution of the dynamic pressure associated with the flow velocity u_{II} is typically around 10% of the static pressure and can therefore be neglected. Geodetic height differences are also negligible. Accordingly, the flow velocity u_{bc} in the breaker gap can be determined using Equation (2.27).

$$u_{\text{I}} = u_{\text{bc}} = \sqrt{\frac{2\Delta p}{\rho\left(1 + \zeta_{\text{bc,in}} + \frac{\lambda\Delta l}{d_{\text{bc}}}\right)}} \quad (2.27)$$

The flow velocity is influenced not only by the pressure difference but also by the pressure loss coefficient $\zeta_{\text{bc,in}}$ caused by the cross-sectional change at the inlet, the wall friction along the component length Δl , the pipe friction coefficient λ , and the hydraulic diameter d_{bc} for the whole cross sectional area of the breaker channel. For simplicity, all these influences are combined into an effective friction loss coefficient ζ_{bc} (Equation (2.28)).

$$\zeta_{\text{bc}} = \sqrt{\frac{1}{\left(1 + \zeta_{\text{bc,in}} + \frac{\lambda\Delta l}{d_{\text{bc}}}\right)}} \quad (2.28)$$

With these considerations, the flow velocity in the breaker gap can be determined using Equation (2.29).

$$u_{\text{bc}} = \zeta_{\text{bc}}\sqrt{\frac{2\Delta p}{\rho}} \quad (2.29)$$

Due to flow losses at the gaps, the side channel not only carries the actual conveyed flow \dot{V}_{N} but also the gap flow \dot{V}_{sc} , which adds to the total volume transported through it.

$$\dot{V}_{\text{sc}} = \dot{V}_{\text{N}} + \dot{V}_{\text{bc}} \quad (2.30)$$

The mean flow velocity in the side channel can thus be determined according to Equation (2.31).

$$u_{\text{sc}} = \frac{\dot{V}_{\text{N}}}{A_{\text{sc}}} + \frac{A_{\text{bc}}}{A_{\text{sc}}}\zeta_{\text{bc}}\sqrt{\frac{2\Delta p}{\rho}} \quad (2.31)$$

The equations for \dot{m}_{circ} (Equation (2.18)), Δp (Equation (2.25)), u_{sc} (Equation (2.31)), and ω_{sc} (Equation (2.10)) form the core of the fluid dynamic model and constitute a nonlinear system of equations (NLE). The user must specify six quantities describing the pump geometry, as well as the three model parameters ζ_{circ} , ζ_{sc} , and ζ_{bc} , along with the fluid density. The resulting NLE has three unknowns. To calculate the pump characteristic curve, \dot{V}_{N} and \dot{m}_{circ} are provided, and Δp is determined from the fluid dynamic model. Details regarding the application and the required equations are provided in Section 3.3.1.

3 Methods and Materials

3.1 Pump under Consideration

To evaluate the model's performance and verify its applicability to peripheral pumps, it was first calibrated using an experimentally measured pump characteristic curve and subsequently employed to predict additional pump characteristic curves. The predicted curves were then compared with experimental data. This procedure was illustrated for two peripheral pumps of different sizes. Figure 5a shows the smaller pump (Type HMR 020, Fink Chem+Tec GmbH, Germany), while Figure 5b depicts the larger pump (Type HMI 100, K-Engineering GmbH, Germany).

Figure 5: Investigated PPs. a) Type HMR 020. b) Type HMI 100.

The geometric parameters of the pumps, required for the fluid dynamic model (as illustrated in Figure 2), are listed in Table 1.

Table 1: Geometric parameters of the investigated PPs.

		HMR 020	HMI 100
φ_{bc}	/ °	45	45
$r_{imp,i}$	/ mm	10.5	32.5
$r_{imp,o}$	/ mm	15.0	40.0
r_{sc}	/ mm	14.0	38.1
A_{sc}	/ mm ²	29.3	75.1
A_{bc}	/ mm ²	3.50	2.67

To evaluate the transferability of the calibrated model parameters, the pumps should occupy a similar region of the Cordier diagram. Table 2 presents the manufacturer design points of both pumps and the corresponding specific diameter δ^* and specific speed σ^* calculated according to Thomas et al. [17]. Despite relative deviations of -24.4% for the specific diameter and 11.4% for the specific speed both pumps fall clearly within the range of SCPs in the extended Cordier diagram according to Grabow [18], confirming their hydraulic and geometric similarity.

Table 2: Specific diameter δ^* and specific speed σ^* for the investigated PPs at the manufacturer’s design point, used for classification in the extended Cordier diagram.

		HMR 020	HMI 100
$N_{\text{imp,design}}$	/ rpm	2880	2850
$\dot{V}_{N,\text{design}}$	/ L h^{-1}	10	400
Δp_{design}	/ bar	0.5	5
δ^*	/ -	50.5	37.8
σ^*	/ -	8.95×10^{-3}	9.97×10^{-3}

3.2 Experimental Study

3.2.1 Setup Description

Figure 6 depicts the experimental setup used to measure the pump characteristic curves for both peripheral pumps. Each pump (P1) was connected to a reservoir tank (B1) containing deionized water. The pump’s feed line was connected to the bottom of the tank, while the outlet was returned to the tank, forming a closed circulation loop. Pressure sensors (PR1 and PR2) were installed in the feed and outlet lines to measure the static pressure increase across the pump, with data recorded via a data logger. An adjustable valve (V1) in the pump’s outlet line allowed control of the flow rate at a given impeller speed. The flow rate was measured using a flow meter (FI1) positioned in the feed line. Further details on the components used in the experimental setups for both pumps are provided in Supplementary Material S.1.

Figure 6: Experimental setup used to measure the pump characteristic curves for both PPs.

3.2.2 Experimental Procedure

To determine the pump characteristic curves, water from the reservoir tank (B1) was circulated through the test rig. Initially, a target flow rate was set for each pump. The flow rate was subsequently adjusted manually using the needle valve (V1). To ensure steady-state conditions, each pump was operated continuously for at least five minutes prior to measurement.

Due to the typically pulsating pressure profiles of radial pumps, the recorded pressure values were averaged over time to obtain a representative time-averaged pressure increase. Pressure

measurements were recorded every 10 seconds over a period of three minutes for the HMR 020 and five minutes for the HMI 100, respectively. The data were then averaged to calculate the mean pressure difference. For the HMR 020, five impeller speeds N_{imp} (1783 rpm, 2361 rpm, 2946 rpm, 3368 rpm, and 3686 rpm) were investigated, with a maximum flow rate of 1.2 L min^{-1} . For the HMI 100, seven impeller speeds (1179 rpm, 1475 rpm, 1766 rpm, 2055 rpm, 2343 rpm, 2616 rpm, and 2900 rpm) were investigated, with a maximum flow rate of 6 L min^{-1} . For each impeller speed, between seven and twelve distinct operating points—each defined by a pair of pressure difference Δp and nominal flow rate \dot{V}_N —were measured, with a measurement uncertainty of 1.0 % and 2.5 %, respectively.

Further details on the experimental setup and procedure can be found in Eberweiser [19] and Mayer [20].

3.3 Numerical Study

3.3.1 Application of the Fluid Dynamic Model

The fluid dynamic model of PPs derived in Section 2.2 was employed to calculate the pump characteristic curves. Based on the geometry of the side channel and the impeller, the parameters r_{imp} , d_{sc} , r_1 , r_2 , and A_{circ} , were explicitly determined based on the geometric parameters of the side channel and the impeller. The required friction loss coefficients, ζ_{circ} , ζ_{sc} , and ζ_{bc} must be specified. They were calibrated as described in Section 3.3.2. The equations governing the pump's fluid dynamics— \dot{m}_{circ} , Δp , u_{sc} , and ω_{sc} —were then combined into a NLE. The resulting NLE contained three unknowns: the impeller speed ω_{imp} , the nominal volumetric flow rate \dot{V}_N , and the static pressure increase Δp . In the present calculations, ω_{imp} and \dot{V}_N were prescribed, and Δp was obtained as the solution.

The computational procedure, along with the required variables and equations, is illustrated as a flowchart in Figure 7.

Figure 7: Schematic representation of the calculation workflow for determining the pressure increase of the pump Δp for a specified operation point $(\dot{V}_N, \omega_{\text{imp}})$ using the fluid-dynamic model.

3.3.2 Model Calibration

To determine the model parameters ζ_{circ} , ζ_{sc} , and ζ_{bc} required for solving the NLE, the fluid dynamic model was calibrated using a single experimentally measured pump curve for each pump. A parameter estimation approach was employed, with an objective function minimizing the sum of squared residuals between the experimentally measured pressure differences and the values predicted by the model, as defined in Equation (3.1).

$$\min_{\zeta_{\text{circ}}, \zeta_{\text{sc}}, \zeta_{\text{bc}}} = \sum_{i=1}^n \left(\Delta p_{\text{exp}}(\omega_{\text{fit}}, \dot{V}_{N,i}) - \Delta p_{\text{model}}(\omega_{\text{fit}}, \dot{V}_{N,i}, \zeta_{\text{circ}}, \zeta_{\text{sc}}, \zeta_{\text{bc}}) \right)^2 \quad (3.1a)$$

$$\text{s.t. } \zeta_j \geq 0, \quad \forall j \in \{\text{circ}, \text{sc}, \text{bc}\} \quad (3.1b)$$

Since the model was calibrated to a single pump characteristic curve, the impeller speed was fixed at $\omega_{\text{imp}} = \omega_{\text{fit}}$ for all data points. In this context, the index i refers to individual points along the pump characteristic curve, $\dot{V}_{N,i}$ denotes the corresponding flow rates, and n is the total number of measured points for that pump characteristic curve.

For the HMR 020, the model was calibrated using $N_{\text{fit}} = 2946$ rpm, and for the HMI 100, the model was calibrated $N_{\text{fit}} = 2055$ rpm, with $\omega_{\text{fit}} = 2\pi N_{\text{fit}}$, because these impeller speeds lie at the midpoint of the impeller speed range investigated by Eberweiser [19] and Mayer [20], thereby avoiding bias toward either low or high rotational speeds.

To assess the uncertainty of the calibrated parameters and evaluate the model sensitivity, 97.5% confidence intervals were calculated based on the Jacobian matrix of the fluid dynamic model, following the methodology described by Rasmuson [21].

4 Results and Discussion

As described in the previous section, the three friction loss parameters ζ were estimated in this work using the experimental data of one pump characteristic curve. The resulting ζ -values are summarized in Table 3. These calibrated parameters were subsequently employed to predict the remaining pump characteristics, enabling a direct comparison between the model predictions and the experimental measurements.

Figure 8: Pump characteristic curves of the HMR 020 showing the static pressure Δp as a function of the nominal flow rate \dot{V}_N - comparison between experimental measurements and predictions from the calibrated fluid dynamic model. The model was calibrated to the 1946 rpm curve.

Figure 8 shows a comparison between the experimental pump characteristic curves of the HMR 020 measured by Eberweiser [19] and the corresponding model predictions. All curves exhibit the expected monotonic decrease in pressure with increasing flow. The model was calibrated to the 2946 rpm curve, achieving a coefficient of determination of 99.9%. Using the calibrated ζ -values, pump characteristic curves at the remaining speeds were predicted and showed very good agreement with the experimental data. The model accurately reproduces the monotonic decrease across all impeller speeds, with an average error of 2.6% and a maximum error of 7.7%, the largest being observed at the highest speed of 3686 rpm.

Figure 9 shows the comparison between the experimental pump characteristic curves of the HMI 100 measured by Mayer [20] and the corresponding model predictions. All curves exhibit the expected monotonic decrease in pressure with increasing flow. The model was calibrated to the 2055 rpm curve, achieving a coefficient of determination of 99.8%. Using the calibrated ζ -values, pump characteristic curves at the remaining speeds were predicted and show good agreement

Figure 9: Pump characteristic curves of the HMI 100 showing the static pressure Δp as a function of the nominal flow rate \dot{V}_N - comparison between experimental measurements and predictions from the calibrated fluid dynamic model. The model was calibrated to the 2055 rpm curve.

with the experimental data. The mean error is 1.8%, with a maximum error of 2.7% observed at the two highest impeller speeds (2616 and 3686 rpm) near the maximum flow rate.

Table 3: Calibrated model parameters for the HMR 020 and HMI 100 pumps, fitted to the 2946 rpm and 2055 rpm pump characteristic curves, respectively. Values are reported with their 97.5% confidence intervals, indicating the uncertainty of the estimates.

	HMR 020	HMI 100
ζ_{sc}	110 ± 18.1	105 ± 13.5
ζ_{circ}	0.381 ± 0.0279	0.338 ± 0.0127
ζ_{bc}	0.190 ± 0.0891	0.232 ± 0.170

The model predictions show excellent agreement with the experimental data, with a maximum deviation of 7.7%. The largest discrepancies occur at the highest impeller speeds and at the highest flow rates. Nevertheless, the comparison demonstrates that the fluid dynamic model can reliably predict the full pump characteristic curves based on a single calibration curve. The fact that such good agreement is achieved even when extrapolating from only one pump characteristic curve strongly supports the physical validity of the modeling approach.

Table 3 summarizes the calibrated ζ -values for both pumps, along with the 97.5% confidence intervals for each parameter. In both cases, the parameter ζ_{sc} , describing friction losses in the side channel flow, is roughly two orders of magnitude larger than ζ_{circ} and ζ_{bc} , which represent the friction losses in the circulation and breaker channel flows, respectively. For ζ_{sc} , the relative width of the 97.5% confidence interval is 32.9% for the HMR 020 and 25.7% for the HMI 100, indicating that this parameter can be determined with reasonable precision. The relative width for ζ_{circ} is 2.1% and 7.5%, demonstrating that this parameter is accurately determined by the chosen calibration method. This is consistent with its physical significance, as the circulation flow represents the key frictional mechanism in the working principle of peripheral pumps.

In contrast, the relative widths of the confidence intervals for ζ_{bc} are 93.8% and 147% for the

HMR 020 and HMI 100, respectively, indicating that this parameter is poorly constrained. This is likely due to the simplified treatment of gap flows in the present model. Further investigations are required to clarify this issue.

Finally, the comparison of ζ -values between both pump geometries shows only minor deviations, ranging from 4.7% to 12.7% between corresponding coefficients. This consistency validates the physical basis of the model. It further suggests that model parameters derived for one pump may serve as reliable initial estimates for geometrically and hydraulically similar pump designs.

In summary, the comparison between the experimentally measured pump characteristic curves and the predictions of the calibrated fluid dynamic model demonstrates that the model can be used to accurately extrapolate and predict the design pump characteristic curves. The comparison of the calibrated friction loss parameters shows only minor deviations between both pumps. These findings validate the physical basis of the proposed model and suggest that the calibrated parameters can be reliably applied to investigate similar pump designs.

5 Conclusion and Outlook

In this study, a fluid dynamic model for PPs was developed based on the approach for SCPs proposed by Muschelknautz [14]. The model was calibrated using a single experimental pump characteristic curve for two pump geometries, HMR 020 and HMI 100, and subsequently applied to predict additional pump curves

The results indicate that the developed model can reliably predict complete pump characteristics based on minimal calibration data. Pump characteristic curves were reproduced with a maximum deviation of 7.7%, demonstrating the strong predictive capability of the approach. The calibrated friction loss parameters, ζ_{sc} , ζ_{circ} , and ζ_{bc} , show only minor deviations between the two investigated pumps, further confirming the physical consistency of the model. However, the relative widths of the 97.5% confidence intervals for ζ_{bc} were 93.8% and 147% for the HMR 020 and HMI 100, respectively, which is likely a result of the simplified treatment of gap flows. This finding highlights opportunities for future refinement of the model, particularly through the inclusion of additional gap flow contributions. Overall, the findings validate the physical basis of the proposed model and suggest that the calibrated parameters can be reliably applied to analyze similar pump designs, making the approach a valuable tool for pump design, performance evaluation, and scale-up. In particular, the presented fluid dynamic model provides reaction engineers with a meaningful framework to investigate the fluid dynamics of PPs and assess their suitability as chemical reactors.

In future work, we will focus on analyzing the internal flow rates predicted by the fluid dynamic model and validating them through experimental measurements or CFD simulations. For further details on a high-resolution CFD model of the HMR 020 developed by our group, the reader is referred to Reviol et al. [22]. Furthermore, coupling the present model with compartment models could provide a more comprehensive description of the flow and reaction behavior within the pump. In addition, extending the model to multiphase flow conditions would significantly broaden its applicability to industrial processes involving gas–liquid or liquid–solid systems. Such developments would further enhance the utility of the model for industrial applications and provide deeper insight into the fluid dynamic behavior of PPs.

Declarations

Availability of data and materials

All data generated or analysed during this study are included in this published article and its supplementary information files.

Competing interests

The authors declare that they have no competing interests.

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Authors' contributions

Arvid Kraus: Conceptualization, Data curation, Formal analysis, Investigation, Methodology, Project administration, Software, Validation, Writing – original draft, Writing – review & editing

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Nomenclature

Latin letters

A_{bc}	cross section area breaker channel	m^2
A_{sc}	cross section area side channel	m^2
A_{circ}	circulation area between impeller and side channel	m^2
d_{sc}	equivalent diameter side channel	m
d_{bc}	hydraulic diameter breaker channel	m
h	geodetic height	m
Δl	mean length breaker channel	m
L	angular momentum	$kg\ m^2\ s^{-1}$
\dot{L}	angular momentum flux	$kg\ m^2\ s^{-2}$
$\dot{L}_{circ,r2}$	angular momentum flux of circulation flow entering the side channel	$kg\ m^2\ s^{-2}$
$\dot{L}_{circ,r1}$	angular momentum flux of circulation flow leaving the side channel	$kg\ m^2\ s^{-2}$
\dot{m}_{circ}	circulation mass flow	$kg\ s^{-1}$
M	torque	$kg\ m^2\ s^{-2}$
M_p	torque in tangential direction exerted by pressure	$kg\ m^2\ s^{-2}$
M_{fric}	torque in tangential direction exerted by friction	$kg\ m^2\ s^{-2}$
n	number of experimental points	-
N_{imp}	impeller speed	rpm
Δp_{rad}	radial pressure difference	$kg\ m^{-1}\ s^{-2}$
Δp_{sc}	radial pressure difference side channel	$kg\ m^{-1}\ s^{-2}$
Δp_{imp}	radial pressure difference impeller channel	$kg\ m^{-1}\ s^{-2}$
Δp	tangential pressure difference from inlet to outlet	$kg\ m^{-1}\ s^{-2}$
r	radius	m
r_{imp}	mean radius of impeller blades	m
$r_{imp,o}$	outer radius of impeller blades	m
$r_{imp,i}$	inner radius of impeller blades	m
r_{sc}	radius center of gravity side channel cross section	m
r_z	radius circulation center	m
r_2	radius circulation entering the side channel	m
r_1	radius circulation leaving the side channel	m

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u	velocity	m s^{-1}
u_{bc}	average tangential velocity breaker channel	m s^{-1}
u_{circ}	average circulation velocity	m s^{-1}
$u_{imp,local}(r)$	local tangential velocity impeller channel	m s^{-1}
u_{sc}	average tangential velocity side channel	m s^{-1}
$u_{sc,local}(r)$	local tangential velocity side channel	m s^{-1}
\dot{V}_N	nominal flow rate	$\text{m}^3 \text{s}^{-1}$
\dot{V}_{sc}	total flow rate side channel	$\text{m}^3 \text{s}^{-1}$
\dot{V}_{bc}	flow rate breaker channel	$\text{m}^3 \text{s}^{-1}$

Greek letters

δ^*	specific diameter	-
φ_{bc}	central angle breaker block	°
ρ	fluid density	kg m^{-3}
σ^*	specific speed	-
ω_{imp}	angular speed impeller	s^{-1}
ω_{sc}	representative angular speed side channel	s^{-1}
ζ_{sc}	pressure loss coefficient side channel	-
ζ_{bc}	simplified pressure loss coefficient breaker channel	-
$\zeta_{bc,in}$	pressure loss coefficient cross section change breaker channel	-
ζ_{circ}^*	pressure loss coefficient circulation flow	-
ζ_{circ}	simplified pressure loss coefficient circulation flow	-

Subscripts

I	start of side channel
II	end of side channel
design	manufacturer design point

Abbreviations

PP	peripheral pump
SCP	side channel pump